

Paleobiology
Supplementary Information for

A biased fossil record can preserve reliable phylogenetic signal

C. Henrik Woolley^{1,2*}, Jeffrey R. Thompson^{3,4}, Yun-Hsin Wu^{1,2}, David J. Bottjer²,
Nathan D. Smith¹

¹ Dinosaur Institute, Natural History Museum of Los Angeles County, Los Angeles, California,
United States of America

² Department of Earth Sciences, University of Southern California, Los Angeles, California, United
States of America

³ Department of Earth Sciences, The Natural History Museum, London, United Kingdom

⁴UCL Centre for life's origins and evolution, University College London, London, United Kingdom

* Corresponding author: C. Henrik Woolley

Email: chwoolle@usc.edu

This PDF file includes:

Supplementary Text
Figures S1 to S28
Legends for Datasets S1 to S84
SI References

Other supplementary materials for this manuscript include the following:

Datasets S1 to S84

1

2 **Supplementary Discussion**

3 **Discrepancies between in-person and electronic collections database sampling.** We
4 observed several differences between fossil squamate specimens sampled in-person and via
5 electronic collections databases (**Fig. S2A**). In-person sampling yielded a higher proportion of
6 dermal and appendicular skeletal elements than sampled in electronic databases (**Fig. S2A**). One
7 possible reason for the differences in observed dermal skeletal element appearances could be
8 that squamate osteoderms, when preserved, are generally extremely numerous and tedious for
9 collections staff/volunteers to count, and as a result, they are generally batch-catalogued with the
10 label “osteoderms”, or “numerous osteoderms”. While we were able to count the individual
11 osteoderms we sampled in-person, we were not able to count osteoderms in our electronic
12 collections database sample, because this sampling technique relied solely on labels associated
13 with the catalogued specimen. This same possible explanation can be applied to the numerous,
14 small bones that make up the squamate manus and pes (difficult to identify and tedious to count),
15 that lead to the discrepancy between in-person and electronic samples of appendicular elements.
16 These highlighted discrepancies emphasize the importance of increasing in-person access to
17 organized, curated natural history collections, and caution against an exclusive reliance on
18 electronic databases as unbiased sources of natural history data. In addressing broad, regional
19 and global paleobiological questions, in-person and electronic sampling both have limitations, and
20 both were used in this study to account for each method’s shortcomings.

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22 **Supplementary Materials and Methods**

23 **Institutions sampled:** American Museum of Natural History (**AMNH**), New York, New York,
24 United States of America; Denver Museum of Nature & Science (**DMNH**), Denver, Colorado,
25 United States of America; Institute for Vertebrate Paleontology and Paleoanthropology (**IVPP**),
26 Beijing, China; Natural History Museum London (**NHMUK**), London, United Kingdom; Natural
27 History Museum of Los Angeles County (**LACM**), Los Angeles, California, United States of
28 America; The Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History (**USNM**), Washington, D.C.,

29 United States of America; Washington, D.C.; University of Florida Museum of Natural History
30 (**UFMNH**), Gainesville, Florida, United States of America; Yale Peabody Museum of Natural
31 History (**YPM**), New Haven, Connecticut, United States of America.

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33 **In-person sampling of fossil squamate collections.** Taphonomic bias and preservation mode
34 played key roles in the precision of taxon identification and anatomical assignment. Incomplete
35 specimens for which not enough diagnostic information was preserved was often restricted to
36 identification at order/suborder/family taxonomic levels, using generalized anatomical terminology
37 (e.g., “partial jaw bone”, “trunk vertebra”, “metapodial”). More complete specimens could be
38 identified at Genus/Species taxonomic levels, with specific anatomical terminology (e.g., “anterior
39 right maxilla”, “proximal left femur”, etc.).

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41 In-person sampling has a clear advantage over digital collections databases in potential for
42 comprehensive specimen examination: the specimens are physically present with the researcher,
43 making all surficial details of a given fossil available for scrutiny. While in-person examination of
44 fossil data is still arguably the most widely employed sampling method for fossil descriptions,
45 there are important sources of bias within this method to consider. Examples of sources of bias
46 for in-person sampling of fossil squamate morphological data include: **1)** background
47 knowledge/expertise of the researcher, **2)** amount of time made available by a given institution for
48 a researcher to spend in a given collection, **3)** potentially prohibitive financial limitations on the
49 researcher visiting a collection (travel costs, housing/food costs, bench fees, etc.). All three of
50 these sources of bias played a role during in-person surveys of the fossil squamate collections at
51 the Denver Museum of Nature & Science (**DMNS**), Yale Peabody Museum of Natural History
52 (**YPM**) and the American Museum of Natural History (**AMNH**). Time allotted at each institution
53 (roughly 40 days at DMNS as a collections volunteer researcher; one week each at YPM and
54 AMNH as a visiting researcher) resulted in different assessments of fossil squamate skeletal
55 preservation (see supplementary data **S12-S13**). Additionally, these collections visits focused on
56 Late Cretaceous terrestrial squamate collections from western North America, which covers a

57 relatively small geographic range, a narrow range of depositional settings (terrestrial fluvial
58 depositional settings), and only a narrow slice of time in the >242 million-year squamate fossil
59 record. In order to rectify this sampling bias in-person, thousands of hours would need to be
60 spent at dozens of institutions worldwide, which is extremely financially prohibitive and unrealistic.

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62 **Electronic collections databases.** Our criteria for selecting the institutions included in this part
63 of the survey was dependent on readily-available digital vertebrate palaeontology collections
64 databases on the institution's website, with collections data that could be downloaded as .csv files
65 or efficiently converted to a dataframe. The compilation of each dataframe was achieved on each
66 institution's website by a simple keyword search for "Squamata" in the taxonomy category. Once
67 the dataframe of the squamate specimens and their corresponding information was downloaded,
68 we utilized the catalogued specimen labels to discern which elements of the fossil squamate
69 skeleton were included under a given catalogue number. This was accomplished using keyword
70 searches (command/control+F) for each bone in the squamate skeleton (**Supplementary Data**
71 **S1-S14**) in Microsoft Excel.

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73 Because multiple skeletal elements are frequently included under a single specimen catalogue
74 number, our search criterion was "number of occurrences" of a skeletal element on the specimen
75 labels, rather than the number of individual elements with a catalogue number. If specific counts
76 for a given skeletal element was indicated on the specimen label (e.g., vertebra (x35)), that
77 counted number was included in the total specimens from the collection. If no count was included
78 on a specimen label, then we counted the occurrence of that skeletal element as a single
79 occurrence. We designed the keyword searches to be as inclusive as possible regarding the
80 anatomical language on each specimen label. Some specimens had thorough anatomical
81 descriptions (e.g., posterior portion of the left maxilla), while others were more general (e.g., "jaw
82 fragment"). Regardless of level of detail on the label, if an element could be assigned to one of
83 the seven anatomical regions we designated, we included it in the survey. Because our
84 anatomical binning of phylogenetic characters for the assessments of phylogenetic signal uses

85 the same seven anatomical regions (see below), this allowed us to include the specimen data
86 with less specific labels in our characterization of bias in museum collections.

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88 Electronic collections databases, often freely-accessible and allowing for incorporation of more
89 data than a typical research collections visit, are used herein to account for the above
90 shortcomings of in-person collections sampling. However, it is important to acknowledge that the
91 keyword searches of online fossil squamate collections performed herein are inherently biased for
92 several non-insignificant reasons. First, the online collections databases themselves are only
93 partial representations of the entirety of the collection; each of the natural history museums
94 sampled herein are actively digitizing their collections, and not every specimen in the collection
95 has been made available online. Second, our inability to personally examine each specimen in
96 the digital collection forces us to be dependent on the accuracy of the taxonomic and anatomical
97 identifications on the specimen labels, most of which are not published and subject to peer
98 review. Third, the lack of individual skeletal element counts on some specimen labels in our
99 dataset (**Supplementary Data S1-S14**) means that these basic occurrence counts are
100 underestimating the total number of skeletal elements in a given fossil squamate collection.
101 Fourth, this survey only includes collections that have publicly-accessible online collections, and
102 therefore we acknowledge that this excludes the majority of worldwide fossil squamate collections
103 that do not have online digital counterparts. In spite of these limitations, this digital dataset still
104 represents an important tool for estimating bias in the squamate fossil record, and is employed
105 herein to account for limitations related to in-person sampling (see above).

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107 **Consistency Index and Retention Index.** To compare the phylogenetic information preserved in
108 overrepresented vs. underrepresented skeletal elements in our sampling of the squamate fossil
109 record, we employed two widely-used, parsimony-based metrics of homoplasy (Consistency
110 Index, CI¹) and retained synapomorphy (Retention Index, RI²). CI values for a given character
111 across an evolutionary tree are calculated using **Equation 1** below:

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$$CI = \frac{m}{s}$$

113 Where m is equal to the minimum number of state changes of a given character required
114 parsimoniously by any evolutionary tree, and s is equal to the actual number of state changes of
115 a given character observed on a given tree. Possible values range from 0 to 1.0. CI values closer
116 to 1.0 indicate minimal homoplasy across an evolutionary tree according to parsimony, whereas
117 CI values closer to 0 indicate high character state change across an evolutionary tree, and
118 therefore more homoplasy. RI values for a given character across an evolutionary tree are
119 calculated using **Equation 2**:

$$120 \quad RI = \frac{g - s}{g - m}$$

121 Where g is equal to the greatest amount of change that a character requires on any evolutionary
122 tree, and m and s are as defined above. As with CI , possible RI values range from 0 to 1.0. RI
123 values closer to 1.0 indicate no homoplasy, and all similarities in character states among
124 branches and nodes of a tree are a result of homology (synapomorphy). RI values closer to 0
125 indicate that a given character shows as much homoplasy as possible, and that any similarities in
126 character states among branches and nodes of a tree are acquired independently and do not
127 result from homology (synapomorphy).

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129 **The effects of missing and/or non-applicable character scorings on measuring**

130 **phylogenetic signal.** Initial results from the δ -Statistic (**Fig. S6-S9**) revealed that higher median
131 phylogenetic signal is present in characters corresponding to jaws and palate and axial regions of
132 the squamate skeleton. However, further scrutiny revealed that δ -Statistic values for each
133 character have a strong inverse relationship with missing and/or non-applicable character
134 scorings (**Fig. S12, S13**), and that characters corresponding to underrepresented regions had
135 significantly higher median percentages of missing data (**GEA: $p= 0.00011$; SEA: $p= 5.377 \times 10^{-5}$,**
136 **Fig. S11**). Missing data led to higher uncertainty in ancestral probability, which in turn led to lower
137 ranges δ -Statistic values (**Supplementary dataset S47**). As a result, it was not appropriate to
138 include any character data from the GEA and SEA datasets with more than 0% missing data into
139 our analyses. However, characters from overrepresented and underrepresented regions of the

140 squamate skeleton with 0% missing remained and were included in the analysis presented here.
141 Additionally, the ancestral state calculations we used in the software BayesTraits to calculate the
142 **δ -Statistic** cannot calculate values for constant characters (e.g., characters that have the same
143 score for all taxa included in the analysis). This resulted in close to two-thirds of the original
144 amount of characters having to be removed from our analyses. Despite the removal of a large
145 amount of phylogenetic data for the **δ -Statistic**, we still retained enough data to observe
146 meaningful patterns in phylogenetic signal among our anatomical regions in both limbed
147 squamates (i.e., most lizards) and limbless squamates (i.e., snakes, amphisbaenians, dibamids,
148 other limbless lizards).

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150 Because of the extreme disparities in bauplans among extant limbed lizards and limbless groups
151 of squamates, it is unsurprising that there would be a large amount of missing/non-applicable
152 characters, particularly those associated with the pectoral girdle, pelvic girdle, and appendicular
153 elements. To minimize the limbed/limbless disparities in applicable characters, we ran the **δ -**
154 **Statistic** analyses for limbed taxa and limbless taxa for both the **GEA** and **SEA** datasets (**Figure**
155 **S14-S18, Supplementary Data S48-S57**). We also removed five legged squamate taxa from the
156 **GEA** dataset due to the fact that they were only scored for skull characters: *Colobosaura*
157 *modesta*, *Cordylosaurus subtesselatus*, *Xenosaurus platyceps*, *Leiosaurus catamarcensis*, and
158 *Urostrophus vautieri* (**Supplementary Data S48**). Because of the large quantity of snake taxa in
159 the GEA dataset, we also ran an analysis of the **δ -Statistic** using exclusively taxa contained
160 within Serpentes (**Supplementary Data S52, S57, Figure S19**).

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162 While more characters were excluded for the **δ -Statistic** analyses than in our CI and RI analyses,
163 the general patterns in phylogenetic signal were similar among all three analyses. Statistical
164 analyses revealed no significant difference in retained phylogenetic signal among characters
165 corresponding to overrepresented and underrepresented regions of the squamates skeleton in
166 the fossil record. These results show that while we could only include characters for which every
167 taxon could be scored in calculating the **δ -Statistic**, our three measurements of phylogenetic

168 signal, using different evolutionary frameworks and different hypotheses of squamate
169 relationships (GEA, SEA), produced similar results.

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 196 **Figure S1.** Schematic diagram of an example squamate skeleton (modeled after *Uta*
 197 *stansburiana*, lower image), with colorized anatomical regions used in this study for sampling of
 198 fossil squamate collections, and example fossil squamate elements. **A)** Jaws and palatal
 199 elements (inset: DMNH EPV.119554 Scincomorpha partial left dentary, from Woolley, Smith &
 200 Sertich (2020)³. **B)** Posterior cranial elements (inset: YPM (unnumbered), partial frontal). **C)**
 201 Dermal elements (osteoderms) (inset: DMNH EPV.119455, Anguinae osteoderm, from Woolley,
 202 Smith & Sertich (2020)³. **D)** Axial elements (inset: UU MAA 7173, *Ophisaurus* partial trunk
 203 vertebra, from Georgalis et al. (2019)⁴. **E)** Pectoral girdle (inset: YPM 3230, *Polyglyphanodon*
 204 *sternbergi* scapulocoracoid) **F)** Appendicular elements (inset: YPM 3230, *Polyglyphanodon*

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sternbergi forelimb) **G**) Pelvic girdle (inset: YPM 3230, *Polyglyphanodon sternbergi* incomplete pelvis).

Yale Peabody Museum- Vertebrate Paleontology Collections online collections database search workflow

1. Go to: <https://collections.peabody.yale.edu/search/>

The Yale Peabody Museum of Natural History encourages the use of its collections for research, publication, exhibition, education and other purposes. At this site you can explore more than five million specimens and objects currently catalogued in our collections. In a Basic Search you can enter one or more keywords and use quotes to indicate exact terms. You can also narrow results by subject matter by choosing one of the collections below. In an Advanced Search you can filter by specific terms (such as locations, dates, scientific names) using the drop down menus. For more help click the links under Search Tips on the Advanced Search page. Please bear in mind that electronic collections data are only proxies for the actual specimens and artifacts, and although these are checked regularly for discrepancies, no guarantee of accuracy is extended here. Contact the Collections Manager for the appropriate Yale Peabody Museum Division if you have questions, particularly if you wish to publish using material obtained from this service. In keeping with Yale University's Open Access Policy, all data and imagery at this site are made available under a CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication. By accessing our website and images you agree to our Terms of Use.

2. Click on "Vertebrate Paleontology"

3. Type in "Squamata" in "Advanced Search"

4. Check "is Fossil" under "Limit To"

5. Click "Export Records":
"Export to CSV (Limit 500)".
Repeat exports for all specimens

Figure S2. Workflow for keyword search-sampling Yale Peabody Museum's electronic collections database.

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Figure S3. Distribution skeletal elements sampled and sourced phylogenetic characters. **A)** Distributions of skeletal element occurrences. **B)** Distributions of phylogenetic characters per anatomical region of both datasets used in this study^{5,6}.

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Figure S4. Distributions of CI and RI values per anatomical bin for the GEA dataset⁵. **A)** Consistency Index distributions. **B)** Retention Index distributions.

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Figure S5. Distributions of CI and RI values per anatomical bin for the SEA dataset⁶. **A)** Consistency Index distributions. **B)** Retention Index distributions.

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Figure S6. Summary of parsimony-based measurements of phylogenetic signal, with character matrices and topologies swapped. **A)** Distribution of CI values for **GEA matrix vs. SEA topology** characters corresponding to overrepresented skeletal elements in the squamate fossil record (See inset, center: overrepresented and underrepresented fossil skeletal regions mapped onto a schematic diagram of *U. stansburiana*) and all underrepresented skeletal elements in the squamate fossil record. **B)** Distribution of RI values for same **GEA matrix vs. SEA topology** character bins as in (A). **C)** Distribution of CI values of **SEA matrix vs. GEA topology** characters. **D)** Distribution of RI values of **SEA matrix vs. GEA topology** characters.

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Figure S7. Distributions of CI and RI values per anatomical bin for the GEA matrix vs. SEA topology dataset. **A)** Consistency Index distributions. **B)** Retention Index distributions.

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Figure S8. Distributions of CI and RI values per anatomical bin for the SEA matrix vs. GEA topology dataset. **A)** Consistency Index distributions. **B)** Retention Index distributions.

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Figure S9. Sample visual representations of the calculations of node probabilities, using the SEA dataset⁶ in BayesTraits (Meade & Pagel, 2016⁷). **A)** overrepresented and underrepresented fossil skeletal regions mapped onto a schematic diagram of *Uta stansburiana*. **B)** Ancestral state probabilities (node entropies) for example character corresponding to overrepresented fossil squamate skeletal elements (Premaxilla, green color palette) and underrepresented fossil squamate skeletal elements (Parietal, blue color palette).

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Distribution of δ : Gauthier et al. (2012)

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Figure S10. Summary of distributions of δ -Statistic⁸ values for the GEA⁵ dataset using time-calibrated fossil tips and 1 million-year uniform branch lengths.

Distribution of δ : Gauthier et al. (2012)

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Figure S11. Summary of distributions of δ -Statistic⁸ values for the GEA⁵ dataset using time-calibrated fossil tips and 3 million-year uniform branch lengths.

Distribution of δ : Gauthier et al. (2012)

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Figure S12. Summary of distributions of δ -Statistic⁸ values for the GEA⁵ dataset using time-calibrated fossil tips and 5 million-year uniform branch lengths.

Distribution of δ : Simões et al. (2018)

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Figure S13. Summary of distributions of δ -Statistic⁸ values for the SEA⁶ dataset.

Gauthier et al. (2012): Missing character data

Simões et al. (2018): Missing character data

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Figure S14. Correlation between % Missing/non-applicable character scorings (x-axis) and overrepresented/underrepresented fossil squamate skeletal regions. For both phylogenetic datasets, underrepresented fossil skeletal regions from our initial sampling have a higher frequency of missing/non-applicable character scorings.

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Simões et al. (2018): % Missing character data vs. δ - values

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Figure S16. XY scatterplot of the relationship between % Missing/non-applicable character scorings vs. δ -statistic values of characters in the Simões et al. (2018) dataset. Data is separated into overrepresented (blue) and underrepresented (orange) anatomical regions in the squamate fossil record.

Distribution of δ : Gauthier et al. (2012)

Legged taxa; dated fossil tips + dated internal nodes;
3 m.y. uniform branch lengths

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Figure S17. Summary of distributions of δ -Statistic⁸ values for legged taxa from the GEA⁵ dataset using time-calibrated fossil tips, 78 calibrated internal nodes from Pyron (2017)⁹ and 3 million-year uniform branch lengths.

Distribution of δ : Gauthier et al. (2012)

Legged taxa; dated fossil tips + dated internal nodes;
5 m.y. uniform branch lengths

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Figure S18. Summary of distributions of δ -Statistic⁸ values for legged taxa from the GEA⁵ dataset using time-calibrated fossil tips, 78 calibrated internal nodes from Pyron (2017) and 5 million-year uniform branch lengths.

Distribution of δ : Gauthier et al. (2012)

Legged taxa; dated fossil tips + dated internal nodes;
7 m.y. uniform branch lengths

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Figure S19. Summary of distributions of δ -Statistic⁸ values for legged taxa from the GEA⁵ dataset using time-calibrated fossil tips, 78 calibrated internal nodes from Pyron (2017) and 7 million-year uniform branch lengths.

Distribution of δ : Simões et al. (2018) Legged Taxa

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Figure S20. Summary of distributions of δ -Statistic⁸ values for the SEA⁶ dataset, using only legged taxa (incomplete).

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Figure S21. Distributions of δ -Statistic for the pruned **GEA** character dataset using only taxa belonging to Serpentes (prior on transition rates for ancestral node probability calculations = 0.01). Inset: overrepresented and underrepresented fossil skeletal regions mapped onto a schematic diagram of *Crotalus atrox*. Histogram shows the distribution of δ -values between **GEA** characters (time-calibrated fossil tips +78 calibrated internal nodes with minimum branch lengths of 5 million years) corresponding to overrepresented (green) and underrepresented (blue) fossil squamate skeletal elements.

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Figure S22. Summary of distributions of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing data in the GEA⁵ dataset using only limbed squamate taxa, time-calibrated fossil tips + 78 calibrated internal nodes, 5 million-year uniform branch lengths and prior character transition rate of 0.01.

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Figure S23. Summary of distributions of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing data in the SEA⁶ dataset, using only limbed squamate taxa and a prior character transition rate of 0.01.

Distribution of δ -values (Prior transition rate = 0.01): Gauthier et al. (2012)
Legless squamates

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Figure S24. Summary of distributions of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing data in the GEA⁵ dataset using only limbless squamate taxa, time-calibrated fossil tips +78 calibrated internal nodes, 5 million-year uniform branch lengths and prior character transition rate of 0.01.

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Figure S25. Summary of distributions of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing data in the GEA⁵ dataset using only taxa included in Serpentes (snakes), time-calibrated fossil tips +78 calibrated internal nodes, 5 million-year uniform branch lengths and prior character transition rate of 0.01.

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Figure S26. Summary of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing data, using swapped character matrices and topologies. **A) GEA Matrix vs SEA Topology. B) SEA Matrix vs. GEA Topology.**

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Figure S27. Summary of distributions of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing data in the GEA matrix vs. SEA topology dataset, using only limbed squamate taxa and a prior character transition rate of 0.01.

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Figure S28. Summary of distributions of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing data in the SEA matrix vs. GEA topology dataset, using only limbed squamate taxa and a prior character transition rate of 0.01.

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377 **Dataset S1 (separate file).** Source dataframe for fossil squamate electronic collections database
378 from the Institute for Vertebrate Paleontology & Paleoanthropology (IVPP), Beijing, China.

379 **Dataset S2 (separate file).** Source dataframe for fossil squamate electronic collections database
380 from the Natural History Museum of Los Angeles County (LACM), Los Angeles, California, USA.

381 **Dataset S3 (separate file).** Source dataframe for fossil squamate electronic collections database
382 from the Natural History Museum London (NHMUK), London, UK.

383 **Dataset S4 (separate file).** Source dataframe for fossil squamate electronic collections database
384 from the University of Florida Museum of Natural History, Gainesville, Florida, USA.

385 **Dataset S5 (separate file).** Source dataframe for fossil squamate electronic collections database
386 from the Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History (USNM), Washington, D.C., USA.

387 **Dataset S6 (separate file).** Source dataframe for fossil squamate electronic collections database
388 from the Yale Peabody Museum of Natural History (YPM), New Haven, Connecticut, USA.

389 **Dataset S7 (separate file).** Combined dataframe of all specimen information from sampled fossil
390 squamate digital collections

391 **Dataset S8 (separate file).** Dataframe of all skeletal element occurrences assigned to
392 mosasaurs in surveyed digital collections.

393 **Dataset S9 (separate file).** Dataframe of all skeletal element occurrences assigned to lizards in
394 surveyed digital collections.

395 **Dataset S10 (separate file).** Dataframe of all skeletal element occurrences assigned to snakes in
396 surveyed digital collections.

397 **Dataset S11 (separate file).** Dataframe of all skeletal element occurrences assigned to
398 "Squamata indet." in surveyed digital collections.

399 **Dataset S12 (separate file).** Dataframe of all specimen info for squamates surveyed in-person.

400 **Dataset S13 (separate file).** Dataframe of all fossil squamate skeletal element occurrences in in-
401 person collections surveys

402 **Dataset S14 (separate file).** Dataframe summarizing all fossil squamate skeletal element
403 occurrences in surveyed collections.

404 **Dataset S15 (separate file).** .tre file of the Strict Consensus Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ topology
405 used for calculating CI and RI in this study, with fossil taxa dropped.

406 **Dataset S16 (separate file).** .tre file of the Strict Consensus Simões et al. (2018)⁶ topology used
407 for calculating CI and RI in this study, with fossil taxa dropped.

408 **Dataset S17 (separate file).** NEXUS file of the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ topology used for
409 calculating CI and RI in this study, with fossil taxa dropped.

410 **Dataset S18 (separate file).** NEXUS file of the Simões et al. (2018)⁶ topology used for
411 calculating CI and RI in this study, with fossil taxa dropped.

412 **Dataset S19 (separate file).** Dataframe of the average character CI values for the Gauthier et al.
413 (2012)⁵ dataset.

414 **Dataset S20 (separate file).** Dataframe of the average character CI values for the Simões et al.
415 (2018)⁶ dataset.

416 **Dataset S21 (separate file).** Dataframe of the average character RI values for the Gauthier et al.
417 (2012)⁵ dataset.

418 **Dataset S22 (separate file).** Dataframe of the average character RI values for the Simões et al.
419 (2018)⁶ dataset.

420 **Dataset S23 (separate file).** Results of the statistical tests comparing CI and RI value
421 distributions per surveyed anatomical bin in squamate collections.

422 **Dataset S24 (separate file).** NEXUS file of the Bayesian consensus tree from Simões et al.
423 (2018)⁶ dataset, used in our calculation of the δ -Statistic.

424 **Dataset S25 (separate file).** NEXUS file of the strict consensus tree from the Gauthier et al.
425 (2012)⁵ dataset (dated fossil tips with 3 million-year uniform branch lengths), used in our
426 calculation of the δ -Statistic.

427 **Dataset S26 (separate file).** NEXUS file of the strict consensus tree from the Gauthier et al.
428 (2012)⁵ dataset (dated fossil tips with 1 million -year uniform branch lengths), used in our
429 calculation of the δ -Statistic.

430 **Dataset S27 (separate file).** NEXUS file of the strict consensus tree from the Gauthier et al.
431 (2012)⁵ dataset (dated fossil tips with 5 million -year uniform branch lengths), used in our
432 calculation of the δ -Statistic.

433 **Dataset S28 (separate file).** Dataframe of the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ character matrix, with
434 constant characters removed, used for calculation of the δ -Statistic⁸.

435 **Dataset S29 (separate file).** Dataframe of the Simões et al. (2018)⁶ character matrix, with
436 constant characters removed, used for calculation of the δ -Statistic⁸.

437 **Dataset S30 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values from the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵
438 dataset (dated fossil tips with 1 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-0.001).

439 **Dataset S31 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values from the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵
440 dataset (dated fossil tips with 1 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-0.01).

441 **Dataset S32 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values from the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵
442 dataset (dated fossil tips with 1 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-0.1).

443 **Dataset S33 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values from the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵
444 dataset (dated fossil tips with 1 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-1.0).

445 **Dataset S34 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values from the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵
446 dataset (dated fossil tips with 3 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-0.001).

447 **Dataset S35 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values from the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵
448 dataset (dated fossil tips with 3 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-0.01).

449 **Dataset S36 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values from the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵
450 dataset (dated fossil tips with 3 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-0.1).

451 **Dataset S37 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values from the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵
452 dataset (dated fossil tips with 3 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-1.0).

453 **Dataset S38 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values from the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵
454 dataset (dated fossil tips with 5 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-0.001).

455 **Dataset S39 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values from the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵
456 dataset (dated fossil tips with 5 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-0.01).

457 **Dataset S40 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values from the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵
458 dataset (dated fossil tips with 5 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-0.1).

459 **Dataset S41 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values from the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵
460 dataset (dated fossil tips with 5 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-1.0).

461 **Dataset S42 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values from Simões et al. (2018)⁶ dataset
462 (U: 0-0.001).

463 **Dataset S43 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values from Simões et al. (2018)⁶ dataset
464 (U: 0-0.01).

465 **Dataset S44 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values from Simões et al. (2018)⁶ dataset
466 (U: 0-0.1).

467 **Dataset S45 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values from Simões et al. (2018)⁶ dataset
468 (U: 0-1.0).

469 **Dataset S46 (separate file).** Results of bootstrap tests of δ -Statistic⁸ distributions for surveyed
470 anatomical bins for both the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ and Simões et al. (2018)⁶ datasets.

471 **Dataset S47 (separate file).** Data and charts assessing and testing the relationships between
472 the percentage of missing/non-applicable characters and measurements of phylogenetic signal.

473 **Dataset S48 (separate file).** Dataframe of the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ character matrix, with
474 constant characters and characters with missing/non-applicable scores removed and using only
475 limbed squamate taxa, used for calculation of the δ -Statistic⁸.

476 **Dataset S49 (separate file).** Dataframe of the Simões et al. (2018)⁶ character matrix, with
477 constant characters and characters with missing/non-applicable scores removed and using only
478 limbed squamate taxa, used for calculation of the δ -Statistic⁸.

479 **Dataset S50 (separate file).** Dataframe of the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ character matrix, with
480 constant characters and characters with missing/non-applicable scores removed and using only
481 limbless squamate taxa, used for calculation of the δ -Statistic⁸.

482 **Dataset S51 (separate file).** Dataframe of the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ character matrix, with
483 constant characters and characters with missing/non-applicable scores removed and using only
484 snake taxa, used for calculation of the δ -Statistic⁸.

485 **Dataset S52 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing
486 data, using only limbed squamate taxa in the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ dataset (dated fossil tips and
487 78 calibrated internal nodes with 3 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-0.001).

488 **Dataset S53 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing
489 data, using only limbed squamate taxa in the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ dataset (dated fossil tips and
490 78 calibrated internal nodes with 3 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-0.01).

491 **Dataset S54 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing
492 data, using only limbed squamate taxa in the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ dataset (dated fossil tips and
493 78 calibrated internal nodes with 3 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-0.1).

494 **Dataset S55 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing
495 data, using only limbed squamate taxa in the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ dataset (dated fossil tips and
496 78 calibrated internal nodes with 3 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-1.0).

497 **Dataset S56 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing
498 data, using only limbed squamate taxa in the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ dataset (dated fossil tips and
499 78 calibrated internal nodes with 5 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-0.001).

500 **Dataset S57 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing
501 data, using only limbed squamate taxa in the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ dataset (dated fossil tips and
502 78 calibrated internal nodes with 5 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-0.01).

503 **Dataset S58 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing
504 data, using only limbed squamate taxa in the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ dataset (dated fossil tips and
505 78 calibrated internal nodes with 5 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-0.1).

506 **Dataset S59 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing
507 data, using only limbed squamate taxa in the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ dataset (dated fossil tips and
508 78 calibrated internal nodes with 5 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-1.0).

509 **Dataset S60 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing
510 data, using only limbed squamate taxa in the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ dataset (dated fossil tips and
511 78 calibrated internal nodes with 7 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-0.001).

512 **Dataset S61 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing
513 data, using only limbed squamate taxa in the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ dataset (dated fossil tips and
514 78 calibrated internal nodes with 7 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-0.01).

515 **Dataset S62 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing
516 data, using only limbed squamate taxa in the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ dataset (dated fossil tips and
517 78 calibrated internal nodes with 7 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-0.1).

518 **Dataset S63 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing
519 data, using only limbed squamate taxa in the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ dataset (dated fossil tips and
520 78 calibrated internal nodes with 7 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-1.0).

521 **Dataset S64 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing
522 data, using only limbed squamate taxa from Simões et al. (2018)⁶ dataset (U: 0-0.001).

523 **Dataset S65 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing
524 data, using only limbed squamate taxa from Simões et al. (2018)⁶ dataset (U: 0-0.01).

- 525 **Dataset S66 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing
526 data, using only limbed squamate taxa from Simões et al. (2018)⁶ dataset (U: 0-0.1).
- 527 **Dataset S67 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing
528 data, using only limbed squamate taxa from Simões et al. (2018)⁶ dataset (U: 0-1.0).
- 529 **Dataset S68 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing
530 data, using only limbless squamate taxa in the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ dataset (dated fossil tips
531 and 78 calibrated internal nodes with 5 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-0.01).
- 532 **Dataset S69 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing
533 data, using only squamate taxa belonging to Serpentes in the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ dataset
534 (dated fossil tips and 78 calibrated internal nodes with 5 million-year uniform branch lengths, U: 0-
535 0.01).
- 536 **Dataset S70 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing
537 data, using only legged squamate taxa in the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ character matrix mapped
538 onto the Simões et al. (2018)⁶ topology.
- 539 **Dataset S71 (separate file).** Dataframe of δ -Statistic⁸ values for characters with 0% missing
540 data, using only legged squamate taxa in the Simões et al. (2018)⁶ character matrix mapped onto
541 the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ topology.
- 542 **Dataset S72 (separate file).** Dataframe of character CI values for characters with 0% missing
543 data, using only legged squamate taxa in the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ character matrix mapped
544 onto the Simões et al. (2018)⁶ topology.
- 545 **Dataset S73 (separate file).** Dataframe of character CI values for characters with 0% missing
546 data, using only legged squamate taxa in the Simões et al. (2018)⁶ character matrix mapped onto
547 the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ topology.
- 548 **Dataset S74 (separate file).** Dataframe of character RI values for characters with 0% missing
549 data, using only legged squamate taxa in the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ character matrix mapped
550 onto the Simões et al. (2018)⁶ topology.
- 551 **Dataset S75 (separate file).** Dataframe of character RI values for characters with 0% missing
552 data, using only legged squamate taxa in the Simões et al. (2018)⁶ character matrix mapped onto
553 the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ topology.
- 554 **Dataset S76 (separate file).** NEXUS file of the Simões et al. (2018)⁶ character matrix, containing
555 only overlapping extant taxa with the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ dataset, used for calculating CI and
556 RI in this study.
- 557 **Dataset S77 (separate file).** NEXUS file of the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ character matrix,
558 containing only overlapping extant taxa with the Simões et al. (2018)⁶ dataset, used for
559 calculating CI and RI in this study.
- 560 **Dataset S78 (separate file).** Dataframe of the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ character matrix, with
561 constant characters and characters with missing/non-applicable scores removed and using only
562 limbed squamate taxa overlapping with the Simões et al. (2018)⁶ character matrix, used for
563 calculation of the δ -Statistic⁸.
- 564 **Dataset S79 (separate file).** Dataframe of the Simões et al. (2018)⁶ character matrix, with
565 constant characters and characters with missing/non-applicable scores removed and using only

566 limbed squamate taxa overlapping with the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ character matrix, used for
567 calculation of the δ -Statistic⁸.

568 **Dataset S80 (separate file).** NEXUS file of the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ tree, using only limbed
569 squamate taxa overlapping with the Simões et al. (2018)⁶ tree used for calculation of the δ -
570 **Statistic⁸.**

571 **Dataset S81 (separate file).** NEXUS file of the Simões et al. (2018)⁶ tree, using only limbed
572 squamate taxa overlapping with the Gauthier et al. (2012)⁵ tree, used for calculation of the δ -
573 **Statistic⁸.**

574 **Dataset S82 (separate file).** NEXUS file of the strict consensus tree from the Gauthier et al.
575 (2012)⁵ dataset (dated fossil tips with 3 million-year uniform branch lengths with 78 dated internal
576 nodes from Pyron, 2017⁹), used in our calculation of the δ -**Statistic.**

577 **Dataset S83 (separate file).** NEXUS file of the strict consensus tree from the Gauthier et al.
578 (2012)⁵ dataset (dated fossil tips with 5 million -year uniform branch lengths with 78 dated internal
579 nodes from Pyron, 2017⁹), used in our calculation of the δ -**Statistic.**

580 **Dataset S84 (separate file).** NEXUS file of the strict consensus tree from the Gauthier et al.
581 (2012)⁵ dataset (dated fossil tips with 7 million -year uniform branch lengths with 78 dated internal
582 nodes from Pyron, 2017⁹), used in our calculation of the δ -**Statistic.**

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